

BARRIERS AND DETERMINANTS OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH ACCESS: A SOCIOCULTURAL ANALYSIS OF WOMEN IN OGBOMOSO, NIGERIA

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Abstract: Reproductive health is a vital aspect of women's overall well-being, yet numerous women in Nigeria encounter ongoing barriers to obtaining quality reproductive healthcare. This study examines the sociodemographic and cultural factors that affect access to reproductive health services and the decision-making processes surrounding contraceptive use among women in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. A descriptive cross-sectional survey was conducted involving 354 women of reproductive age (15–49 years) in the Ogbomoso North Local Government Area. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using IBM SPSS (version 28). Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and Spearman's correlation were employed to explore the relationships among sociodemographic variables, cultural influences, and access to reproductive health services. The findings revealed that access to reproductive health services was relatively high, at 83.9% among respondents. Significant associations were found between access and services and marital status ($p = 0.015$) and employment status ($p = 0.022$). However, factors such as education level, income, religion, and place of residence did not show significant relationships. Cultural expectations were notably correlated with women's autonomy in contraceptive use ($\rho = 0.205$, $p < 0.01$), whereas religious beliefs and leadership did not exhibit significant correlations. The major barriers identified included cost (93.6%), spousal disapproval (71.7%), and spiritual beliefs (60.3%). Socio-economic and cultural factors significantly shape women's reproductive health choices in Ogbomoso. The paper, therefore, emphasizes targeted intervention to address financial barriers, encourage male participation, and challenge restrictive cultural norms to enhance access and autonomy in reproductive healthcare.

Keywords: Reproductive health, contraceptive use, sociodemographic factors, cultural beliefs, Women, Ogbomoso, Nigeria.

Introduction

Women's reproductive health remains a crucial component of public health globally, significantly impacting women's overall well-being, autonomy, and socioeconomic development. The World Health Organization reported that approximately 295,000 women lost their lives due to pregnancy and childbirth complications in 2017, with 94% of these fatalities taking place in low- and middle-income nations (World Health Organization, 2023). In Nigeria, women of reproductive age encounter considerable difficulties related to reproductive health.

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The nation has one of the highest maternal mortality ratios in the world, with an estimated maternal mortality ratio (MMR) of 576 deaths for every 100,000 live births, which positions Nigeria among the countries with the highest MMR globally (World Health Organization, 2023). Factors contributing to this high MMR include limited access to quality healthcare, low contraceptive prevalence, and sociocultural barriers. Forty million women of childbearing age (between 15 and 49 years) face significantly high health risks related to childbirth. Although Nigeria comprises only a small fraction of the global population (2.4%), it disproportionately contributes to maternal mortality, accounting for an estimated 10% of all maternal deaths globally (Nigeria Health Watch, 2023; World Health Organization, 2023). This alarming figure reflects a deep systemic gap in healthcare access and use. Contraceptive use in Nigeria is notably low, with only about 20% of currently married women utilizing modern contraceptive methods. This statistic highlights a significant gap in family planning, as there is an unmet need for contraceptive services affecting around 19% of women who wish to prevent pregnancy but lack access to reliable methods (United Nations Children's Fund, 2020). Several sociodemographic factors play a crucial role in influencing contraceptive use across the country. Higher educational attainment has been associated with a greater likelihood of modern contraceptive use, as it often enhances awareness and agency in reproductive decision-making (Abubakar & Abubakar, 2023). In addition, the distinction between urban and rural living conditions is significant. Women residing in urban areas typically have greater access to family planning resources and information, resulting in higher rates of contraceptive use compared with those living in rural settings (Abubakar & Abubakar, 2023; Adedini, Ntoimo, & Alex-Ojei, 2023)

In Oyo State, approximately 262 maternal deaths per 100,000 live births are recorded annually. While this rate is below the national average, it remains troubling, given the state's levels of literacy and socio-economic development. For instance, in Ibadan, the state capital, the Contraceptive Prevalence Rate (CPR) currently stands at 22%. This rate could be compared to other state capitals, such as Benin at 26.6%, Ilorin at 24.6%, and significantly lower than Lagos with 49.6% (Oyo State Ministry of Health, 2025). There is a significant opportunity to enhance the contraceptive prevalence rate (CPR), especially among the urban poor. According to the 2018 Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS), approximately 76% of the urban poor in Oyo State do not utilize any form of contraception, with only around 20% using modern contraceptive methods (National Population Commission, 2019).

Reproductive health outcomes in Ogbomoso are influenced by factors such as education, marital status, age, and socioeconomic conditions. These factors influence reproductive health outcomes in Ogbomoso (Olugbenga-Bello et al., 2016). Despite the growing awareness of contraception and family planning services, studies reveal persistent gaps in utilization and accessibility. For instance, although awareness of contraceptives is widespread in the region, only 25.4% of women of reproductive age in Ogbomoso actively use them (Olugbenga-Bello et al., 2016). Studies (Andeskebtso & Ugochukwu, 2023; Barrow, Isah, Reynolds, & Aisien, 2022; Kasso & Alegbeleye, 2023; Maigoro et al., 2023; Obuna & Uche-Nwidagu, 2024) have revealed the main determinants of contraceptive use, including age of women, higher educational attainment, women's empowerment, marital status, and positive attitudes toward contraception, yet barriers such as fear of side effects, socio-cultural norms, and economic dependency limit uptake. Although there are national and regional data on how sociodemographic factors influence reproductive health, there is a lack of detailed data specific to Ogbomoso. This includes information categorized by age groups, education levels, and distinctions between rural and urban areas. Most studies either generalize findings across southwestern Nigeria or do not deeply analyze intra-community variations in reproductive health outcomes, particularly in semi-urban settings like Ogbomoso, where traditional and modern health systems co-exist. Therefore, this study examines sociodemographic and cultural factors impacting women's contraceptive use in Ogbomoso.

Research Questions

1. What sociodemographic characteristics are significantly associated with access to reproductive health services?
2. How do cultural and religious influences affect contraceptive decision-making among women in Ogbomoso?

Methods and Materials

Study Area

Ogbomoso North Local Government Area (LGA) is a prominent area in Oyo State, located in the southwestern region of Nigeria. This LGA is part of the larger Ogbomoso metropolitan area, bordered by other LGAs, including Ogbomoso South to the south, Surulere to the east, and Orire to the north, with its northeastern edge adjacent to Kwara State. The administrative centre is located in Kinnira, which is within Ogbomoso town and serves as the urban nucleus of the LGA. Ogbomoso is a vibrant and semi-urban LGA with a diverse population engaged in civil service, trading, vocational and farming. The large number of students in Ogbomoso reflects the presence of numerous government institutions and educational facilities, such as Ladoke Akintola University of Technology (LAUTECH) and Bowen University Teaching Hospital, situated within this LGA, which play a significant role in shaping the academic, economic, and social dynamics of the community. According to (City Population, 2022), Ogbomoso North has an estimated population of 284,200, which includes about 62,524 women of reproductive age (15-49 years).

Study Population

All consenting women of reproductive age (15–49 years) in the study area were considered.

Study Design and Sampling

The study employs a descriptive survey design to examine the sociodemographic and cultural factors impacting women's reproductive health in Ogbomoso. It focuses on the sociodemographic, cultural, religious and economic factors that influence contraceptive use. It employs a descriptive survey design because it allows for the utilization of a questionnaire and enables the selection of a large sample size for data collection (Babbie, Mouton, Vorster, & Prozesky, 2012). The subsequent steps were followed to determine the sample size for the study.

The sample size for a population of 62,524 was calculated using Cochran's formula (Cochran, 1977)

The formula is:

$$n_0 = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{e^2}$$

Where:

Z = Z-Score (1.96 for 95% confidence level)

o p = estimated proportion (commonly assumed as 0.5 for maximum variability)

e = margin of error (commonly set to 0.05 or 5%)

Substituting the values:

$$n_0 = \frac{(1.96)^2 \cdot 0.5 \cdot (1 - 0.5)}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n_0 = \frac{3.8416 \cdot 0.25}{0.0025} = 384.16$$

Thus, the initial sample size (n) is approximately 385.

Thus, respondents were selected from the ten (10) political wards in the LGA. These wards serve as the smallest administrative and electoral units. They are essential for organizing local governance, health services, data collection and elections. The wards include Abogunde, Aaje/Ogunbado, Aguodo/Masifa, Isale Afon, Isale Alaasa, Isale Ora/Saja, Jagun, Okelerin, Osupa, and Sabo/Tara. A systematic sampling technique was employed, selecting

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every 10th household (Blanche, Durrheim, & Kelly, 2006). From each ward, 38 households were randomly selected, except for the Sabo/Taara ward, which had a larger population and thus included 43 respondents. In each household, every woman of reproductive age who met the criteria for selection was selected, making a total sample size of 385 for the study.

Participant Selection

In this study, a systematic sampling technique was used to select participants. This ensured that all reproductive-age women who gave their consent to participate were included.

Inclusion Criteria

Eligible participants were women aged 15 to 49 years who expressed their willingness to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Women outside the reproductive age range of 15 to 49 years or who did not consent to participate were excluded from the study.

Data Collection

The study utilizes a questionnaire design consisting of sixteen items focusing on sociodemographic factors and women's reproductive health in Ogbomoso. This questionnaire is divided into three main sections: Section A collects personal information, including age, marital status, educational attainment, employment status, monthly income, and religion. Section B comprises five items related to access to reproductive health services, while Section C addresses cultural and religious influences with another five items. Specialists in Test and Measurement from Ladoko Akintola University of Technology in Ogbomoso assessed the face and content validity of the items to ensure they were clearly defined, relevant, and aligned with the intended constructs. The instrument's reliability was established through an internal consistency test, which resulted in a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.82. The questionnaires were designed to be self-administered to encourage independent and unbiased responses, with assistance from two research aides skilled in reading and writing Yoruba. The data gathering occurred between January 13, 2025, and March 14, 2025.

Measurement of the variables

The explanatory variable in this study was sociodemographic and cultural factors measured by (i) demographic information and (ii) cultural and religious influences. The variables adjusted for in this study were selected background characteristics of respondents including age [under 20, 20–29, 30–39, 40–49], marital status [single, married], level of education [none, primary, secondary, OND/NCE, HND/first degree, postgraduate], employment status [unemployed, employed], Place of residence [urban, rural] and monthly income [<₦70,000, >₦70,000] The outcome variable was the use of reproductive healthcare services proxied by two variables with an affirmative answer assigned “1” and a negative answer assigned “0” for the two questions.

Data Analysis

In this study, data analysis was conducted using IBM SPSS version 28 (George & Mallery, 2014). The data were analyzed for frequency distributions related to the socio-demographic and socio-cultural variables among the participants. Subsequently, cross-tabulation analyses were performed, employing the chi-square test and correlation analysis to evaluate the relationship between each predictor variable and the outcome variable, aiming to identify statistically significant associations. A univariate analysis was also conducted on all independent variables linked to reproductive health services.

Ethical Consideration

The study underwent an ethical review and received approval from the Ethical Research Committee at Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomoso, under Approval Number: ERCBMSLAUTECH:090/01/2025. Before distributing the questionnaires, permission was secured, as this is a fundamental ethical requirement for any research. Informed consent was also obtained from the respondents before collecting any data, ensuring the security of their information. The primary objective of the research was communicated to the respondents as well.

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Throughout the study, a strong commitment to respecting the privacy of all participants was maintained by following ethical principles.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic and cultural factors impacting access to reproductive health services among respondents

Access to reproductive health services					
Variables	Yes (n=297) n (%)	No (n=57) n (%)	Total (n=354) n (%)	Chi-square	p-value
Age of women in years					
<20	29 (85.3)	5 (14.7)	34 (100.0)	0.636	0.888
20 - 29	58 (86.6)	9 (13.4)	67 (100.0)		
30 - 39	151 (83.4)	30 (16.6)	181 (100.0)		
40 - 49	59 (81.9)	13 (18.1)	72 (100.0)		
Marital status					
Single	44 (73.3)	16 (26.7)	60 (100.0)	5.969	0.015*
Married	253 (86.1)	41 (13.9)	294 (100.0)		
Educational level					
No formal education	2 (100.0)	0 (0.0)	2 (100.0)	2.116	0.833
Primary education	14 (82.4)	3 (17.6)	17 (100.0)		
Secondary education	38 (86.4)	6 (13.6)	44 (100.0)		
OND/NCE	76 (87.4)	11 (12.6)	87 (100.0)		
HND/First degree	139 (82.2)	30 (17.8)	169 (100.0)		
Postgraduate degree	28 (80.0)	7 (20.0)	35 (100.0)		
Employment status					
Unemployed	59 (75.6)	19 (24.4)	78 (100.0)	3.278	0.022*
Employed	238 (86.2)	38 (13.8)	276 (100.0)		
Monthly income					
<₦70,000	237 (84.3)	44 (15.7)	281 (100.0)	0.198	0.387
>₦70,000	60 (82.2)	13 (17.8)	73.0 (100.0)		
Religion					
Traditional Christianity	10 (71.4)	4(28.6%)	14 (100.0)	3.259	0.353
Christianity	138 (82.6)	29 (17.4)	167 (100.0)		
Islam	134 (87.0)	20 (13.0)	154 (100.0)		
Others	15 (78.9)	4 (21.1)	19 (100.0)		
Place of residence					
Urban	198 (85.3)	34 (14.7)	232 (100.0)	1.043	0.192
Rural	99 (81.1)	23 (18.9)	122 (100.0)		
Religious beliefs' influence					
Yes	229 (85.1)	40 (14.9)	269 (100.0)	1.258	0.17
No	68 (80.0)	17 (20.0)	85.0 (100.0)		

* =Statistical significance at p<0.05

Table 1 summarizes the analysis of the socio-demographic and cultural factors influencing women’s access to reproductive health. Access to reproductive health facilities is higher among married women, at 253 (86.1%), than among single women, who have 44 (73.3%). These differences were statistically significant ($\chi^2=5.969$, $df=1$, $p=<.05$). A similar pattern is observed regarding employment status: employed women, at 238 (86.2%), have slightly higher access than unemployed women, at 59 (75.6%). The chi-square test results indicate that the observed differences are statistically significant ($\chi^2=5.049$, $df=1$, $p=<.05$). In contrast, no statistically significant differences were found with other variables. For the age of the respondents, the age group of 20-29 has the highest

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proportion of individuals with access to healthcare facilities (86.6%). On the other hand, the 40-49 age group had the lowest access rate (81.9%). In summary, 83.9% of all respondents had access, leaving 16.1% without access. Although access rates were generally high across education levels, women with OND/NCE qualifications reported slightly higher access (87.4%) than those with postgraduate degrees (80%). This variation, however, was not statistically significant.

For income, most respondents, 84.3%, earned less than ₦70,000 National Minimum Wage, while 82.2 % earned above the ₦70,000 National Minimum Wage. There is a minimal deviation between income level and access for the respondents. Islam (87.0%), Christianity (82.6%), Others (78.9%) and Traditional (71.4%) of the respondents had access to reproductive health facilities. The urban (85.3%) respondents had access to healthcare facilities more than the rural (81.1%) residents. A higher proportion (18.9%) of the rural residents lack access compared to urban residents (14.7%). Most respondents (85.1%) influenced by religion and (80.0%) not influenced by religion had access to health facilities.

Table 2:

Table 2: Relationship between sociocultural factors and women’s reproductive decision making

			I can decide whether to use contraceptives or not	Religious beliefs influence my decision	Cultural expectations affect how I plan my family	Religious leaders influence reproductive decisions
Spearman's rho	I can decide whether to use contraceptives or not	Correlation	1.000	-0.100	.205**	0.008
		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)		0.061	0.000	0.878
		N	354	354	354	354
	Religious beliefs influence your decision	Correlation	-0.100	1.000	0.060	-0.034
		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	0.061		0.258	0.524
		N	354	354	354	354
	Cultural expectations affect how I plan my family	Correlation	.205**	0.060	1.000	-0.052
		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.258		0.325
		N	354	354	354	354
	Religious leaders influence reproductive decisions	Correlation	0.008	-0.034	-0.052	1.000
		Coefficient Sig. (2-tailed)	0.878	0.524	0.325	
		N	354	354	354	354

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

In Table 2, Spearman’s rho correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships among the four variables related to reproductive health decision-making. Cultural expectations were positively and significantly correlated with women’s autonomy in contraceptive decision-making ($\rho = 0.205, p < 0.01$), although there was a positive but weak correlation between individual decision-making about contraceptive use and cultural expectations in family planning. However, no significant correlations were observed among the other variables.

Table 3: Barriers to Accessing Reproductive Health Services in Ogbomoso

		Responses		Percent of Respondents Reporting these Barriers
		N	Percent	
Barriers to accessing reproductive health services ^a	Cost	321	29.2%	93.6%
	Distance	97	8.8%	28.3%
	Lack of awareness	77	7.0%	22.4%
	Spousal disapproval	246	22.3%	71.7%
	Religious beliefs	207	18.8%	60.3%
	Poor services	153	13.9%	44.6%
Total		1101	100.0%	321.0%

a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.

Table 3 presents the frequency distribution and significance of various barriers to accessing reproductive health services as reported by the respondents. The most frequently cited barrier was cost, accounting for 321 (29.2%) responses and impacting 93.6% of respondents. The second most common barrier was spousal disapproval, which accounted for 246 (22.3%) of the responses and affected 71.7% of the respondents. Religious beliefs represented 207 (18.8%) of responses and impact 60.3% of the respondents. In addition, poor service quality was noted by 153 (13.9%) responses and affected 44.6% of respondents. Distance to facilities is also a concern, with 97 (8.8%) of the responses citing it as a barrier and affecting 28.3% of the respondents. Lastly, lack of awareness, although the least mentioned barrier by 77 (7.0%) of the responses, affected 22.4% of the respondents.

Discussion

This study investigates the interplay of sociodemographic and cultural factors that affect women's access to reproductive health services in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. The findings indicate that a substantial majority of women (83.9%) reported access to reproductive healthcare; however, this access is significantly shaped by variables such as marital and employment status that demonstrate statistically significant relationships with service utilization. These observations are consistent with prior research (Barrow et al., 2022; Olugbenga-Bello et al., 2016), which posits that married women and those with economic independence are more likely to engage with and utilize reproductive health services, primarily due to the support from spouses and the autonomy granted by financial independence. Conversely, notably educational attainment, monthly income, and geographic location did not exhibit statistically significant associations with access to reproductive health services. This outcome indicates that systemic and cultural barriers may persist and restrict access even in a relatively educated demographic, where most women hold tertiary qualifications. Earlier national studies (Abubakar & Abubakar, 2023) and (Adedini et al., 2023) recognized education as a potent predictor of contraceptive use. However, the current findings may reflect regional variances or indicate that the marginal effectiveness of education diminishes despite robust systemic barriers.

The analysis also reveals that cultural expectations significantly correlate with women's autonomy in contraceptive decision-making. This observation corroborates (Andeskebtso & Ugochukwu, 2023; Kasso & Alegbeleye, 2023; Kidayi et al., 2015; Obuna & Uche-Nwidagu, 2024) who established that traditional norms,

gender roles, and family size expectations play a crucial role in shaping reproductive choices, particularly within Nigeria's northern and central regions. Interestingly, religious beliefs and the influence of religious leaders did not manifest significant correlations in this context, suggesting that personal and familial cultural norms may exert greater influence than formal religious doctrines. The study further identified critical barriers hindering access to reproductive health services. Principally, financial constraints emerged as the most commonly reported obstacle, affecting 93.6% of respondents, followed by spousal disapproval (71.7%) and the impact of religious beliefs (60.3%). These patterns affirm the findings of (Kasso & Alegbeleye, 2023), which identified financial dependence on male partners and socioreligious constraints as significant impediments to women obtaining adequate access to family planning resources in semi-urban and rural contexts. The sustained presence of these barriers, despite the heightened awareness of reproductive health issues, accentuates the urgent necessity for comprehensive interventions that address both structural limitations and sociocultural determinants of health. Furthermore, urban respondents reported marginally higher access rates (85.3%), contrary to their rural counterparts (81.1%). This observation aligns with the national trends highlighted in the NDHS 2018 (National Population Commission, 2019), illustrating geographic disparities in healthcare access and quality. Nonetheless, the absence of statistical significance may denote enhanced service outreach or highlight other influencing factors, such as spousal involvement and cost considerations, which may outweigh geographic advantages. While access to reproductive health services in Ogbomoso appears to be relatively high, the utilization remains constrained by sociocultural and economic factors. The independence of women in reproductive decision-making seems to be predominantly influenced by cultural expectations and economic empowerment rather than solely contingent upon educational levels or religious affiliations. These findings advocate for targeted policy interventions that aim to mitigate financial and cultural obstacles, promote male engagement in family planning education, and improve the accessibility and responsiveness of reproductive health services.

Conclusion

This study examines the sociodemographic and cultural factors affecting women's access to reproductive health services in Ogbomoso, Nigeria. The findings demonstrate that, while the overall access to reproductive healthcare is commendably high among women in this area, specific variables such as marital status and employment significantly influence this access. In contrast, sociodemographic factors, including education level, monthly income, religion, and residential area, did not exhibit statistically significant associations. This study indicates that structural and cultural barriers have a deeper impact on accessibility than the other variables.

Furthermore, the research elucidated that cultural expectations wield considerable influence over women's autonomy in contraceptive decision-making. Notably, religious beliefs and leadership appeared to have a less direct impact on these decisions. Among the key barriers identified to accessing reproductive health services were financial constraints, spousal disapproval, and prevailing religious beliefs. These barriers reflect a complex interplay of economic dependency and socio-cultural norms, which can inhibit women's agency in seeking necessary reproductive health services. The implications of these findings are profound, underscoring the necessity for multifaceted interventions that aim not only to enhance the availability and affordability of reproductive health services but also to critically challenge and reframe cultural narratives that restrict women's autonomy. Policymakers and program designers are encouraged to promote male involvement in family planning, enhance women's economic independence, and expand community-based health education initiatives. Such

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efforts are essential for fostering improved reproductive health outcomes in the Ogbomoso and analogous contexts, ultimately contributing to women's health and well-being. This study adds to the existing literature on women's reproductive health. However, there are some limitations to consider: (a) it depends on quantitative data, which is useful for collecting information from a large sample and identifying trends, but might not fully represent individual experiences, and (b) its results are focused on Ogbomoso, meaning they may not adequately capture the nuances of women's reproductive health in other areas. To overcome these limitations, future research should employ qualitative methods to gain a more comprehensive insight into women's reproductive health.

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